

Figure 2A		Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test								
Two-way RM ANOVA		Matching: Stacked								
Assume sphericity?		Yes								
Alpha		0,05								
Source of Variation		% of total variation	P value	P value summary	Significant?					
Interaction		21.96	<0.0001	****	Yes					
test time		7.639	<0.0001	****	Yes					
treatment-group		35.13	<0.0001	****	Yes					
Subject		20.54	0.0219	*	Yes					
ANOVA table		SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value				
Interaction		0.5906	3	0.1969	F (3, 36) = 25.40	P<0.0001				
test time		0.2054	1	0.2054	F (1, 36) = 26.50	P<0.0001				
treatment-group		0.9447	3	0.3149	F (3, 36) = 20.52	P<0.0001				
Subject		0.5523	36	0.01534	F (36, 36) = 1.980	P=0.0219				
Residual		0.279	36	0.007751						
Test details		Predicted (LS) mean 1	Predicted (LS) mean 2	redicted (LS) mean dif	SE of diff,	N1	N2	t	DF	Adjusted P Value
baseline										
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Vehicle		0.643	0.5628	0.08016	0.04387	12	12	1.827	72	0.4308
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Pregabalin		0.643	0.6016	0.0414	0.04905	12	8	0.8441	72	>0.9999
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+R-715		0.643	0.5961	0.04691	0.04905	12	8	0.9565	72	>0.9999
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Pregabalin		0.5628	0.6016	-0.03876	0.04905	12	8	0.7903	72	>0.9999
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+R-715		0.5628	0.5961	-0.03325	0.04905	12	8	0.6778	72	>0.9999
Reserpine+Pregabalin vs. Reserpine+R-715		0.6016	0.5961	0.005514	0.05373	8	8	0.1026	72	>0.9999
test										
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Vehicle		0.5783	0.1857	0.3926	0.04387	12	12	8.949	72	<0.0001
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Pregabalin		0.5783	0.5516	0.02674	0.04905	12	8	0.5451	72	>0.9999
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+R-715		0.5783	0.6742	-0.09591	0.04905	12	8	1.955	72	0.3265
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Pregabalin		0.1857	0.5516	-0.3658	0.04905	12	8	7.459	72	<0.0001
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+R-715		0.1857	0.6742	-0.4885	0.04905	12	8	9.959	72	<0.0001
Reserpine+Pregabalin vs. Reserpine+R-715		0.5516	0.6742	-0.1226	0.05373	8	8	2.283	72	0.1524

Figure 2A		One-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test								
Test session										
ANOVA table		SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value				
Treatment (between columns)		1,496	3	0,4988	F (3, 36) = 29,08	P<0,0001				
Residual (within columns)		0,6176	36	0,01716						
Total		2,114	39							
Number of families		1								
Number of comparisons per family		6								
Alpha		0,05								
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test		Mean Diff,	95,00% CI of diff,	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P Value				
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Vehicle		0,3926	0,2433 to 0,5419	Yes	****	<0,0001	A-B			
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Pregabalin		0,02674	-0,1402 to 0,1937	No	ns	>0,9999	A-C			
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+R-715		-0,09591	-0,2628 to 0,07101	No	ns	0,7045	A-D			
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Pregabalin		-0,3658	-0,5327 to -0,1989	Yes	****	<0,0001	B-C			
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+R-715		-0,4885	-0,6554 to -0,3216	Yes	****	<0,0001	B-D			
Reserpine+Pregabalin vs. Reserpine+R-715		-0,1226	-0,3055 to 0,06021	No	ns	0,4155	C-D			

Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff,	SE of diff,	n1	n2	t	DF	
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0,5783	0,1857	0,3926	0,05347	12	12	7,341	36	
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Pregabalin	0,5783	0,5516	0,02674	0,05979	12	8	0,4472	36	
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+R-715	0,5783	0,6742	-0,09591	0,05979	12	8	1,604	36	
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Pregabalin	0,1857	0,5516	-0,3658	0,05979	12	8	6,119	36	
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+R-715	0,1857	0,6742	-0,4885	0,05979	12	8	8,17	36	
Reserpine+Pregabalin vs. Reserpine+R-715	0,5516	0,6742	-0,1226	0,06549	8	8	1,873	36	

Figure 2B		Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test									
Two-way RM ANOVA	Matching: Stacked										
Assume sphericity?	Yes										
Alpha	0,05										
Source of Variation	% of total variation	P value	P value summary	Significant?							
Interaction	23.4	0.0002	***	Yes							
test	2.344	0.1186	ns	No							
treatment	20.35	<0.0001	****	Yes							
Subject	20.19	0.941	ns	No							
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value						
Interaction	0.8841	3	0.2947	F (3, 37) = 8.495	P=0.0002						
test time	0.08856	1	0.08856	F (1, 37) = 2.553	P=0.1186						
treatment-group	0.7688	3	0.2563	F (3, 37) = 12.43	P<0.0001						
Subject	0.7629	37	0.02062	F (37, 37) = 0.5943	P=0.9410						
Residual	1.284	37	0.03469								
Test details	Predicted (LS) mean 1	Predicted (LS) mean 2	Predicted (LS) mean diff,	SE of diff,	N1	N2	t	DF	Adjusted P Value		
baseline											
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Vehicle+KOB1	0.5998	0.5727	0.02712	0.07437	10	10	0.3647	74	>0.9999		
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0.5998	0.6342	-0.03443	0.07437	10	10	0.463	74	>0.9999		
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.5998	0.6431	-0.04333	0.07266	10	11	0.5964	74	>0.9999		
Vehicle+KOB1 vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0.5727	0.6342	-0.06156	0.07437	10	10	0.8277	74	>0.9999		
Vehicle+KOB1 vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.5727	0.6431	-0.07046	0.07266	10	11	0.9697	74	>0.9999		
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.6342	0.6431	-0.008899	0.07266	10	11	0.1225	74	>0.9999		
test											
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Vehicle+KOB1	0.578	0.6591	-0.08112	0.07437	10	10	1.091	74	>0.9999		
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0.578	0.2153	0.3626	0.07437	10	10	4.876	74	<0.0001		
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.578	0.7343	-0.1563	0.07266	10	11	2.152	74	0.2081		
Vehicle+KOB1 vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0.6591	0.2153	0.4437	0.07437	10	10	5.967	74	<0.0001		
Vehicle+KOB1 vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.6591	0.7343	-0.07523	0.07266	10	11	1.035	74	>0.9999		
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.2153	0.7343	-0.519	0.07266	10	11	7.142	74	<0.0001		

Figure 2B		One-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test									
Test session											
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value						
Treatment (between columns)	1.62	3	0.5401	F (3, 37) = 20.35	P<0.0001						
Residual (within columns)	0.982	37	0,02654								
Total	2.602	40									
Number of families	1										
Number of comparisons per family	6										
Alpha	0,05										
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff,	95,00% CI of diff,	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P Value						
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Vehicle+KOB1	-0.08112	-0.2842 to 0.1220	No	ns	>0.9999	A-B					
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0.3626	0.1595 to 0.5657	Yes	****	<0.0001	A-C					
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+KOB1	-0.1563	-0.3548 to 0.04208	No	ns	0.2064	A-D					
Vehicle+KOB1 vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0.4437	0.2406 to 0.6468	Yes	****	<0.0001	B-C					
Vehicle+KOB1 vs. Reserpine+KOB1	-0.07523	-0.2737 to 0.1232	No	ns	>0.9999	B-D					
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+KOB1	-0.519	-0.7174 to -0.3205	Yes	****	<0.0001	C-D					

Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	t	DF	
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Vehicle+KOB1	0.578	0.6591	-0.08112	0.07286	10	10	1.113	37	
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0.578	0.2153	0.3626	0.07286	10	10	4.977	37	
Vehicle+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.578	0.7343	-0.1563	0.07118	10	11	2.196	37	
Vehicle+KOB1 vs. Reserpine+Vehicle	0.6591	0.2153	0.4437	0.07286	10	10	6.09	37	
Vehicle+KOB1 vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.6591	0.7343	-0.07523	0.07118	10	11	1.057	37	
Reserpine+Vehicle vs. Reserpine+KOB1	0.2153	0.7343	-0.519	0.07118	10	11	7.291	37	